

Culture Change for Research Data Management at Institutions

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

Griffith University

February 2023

About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

A university-wide review was done to identify the culture of research data management. This review included structured interactions and workshops.

Culture was summarised into three areas of activity:

- Values – What is important to the Individual (researcher) / Institution (university)
- Aims – What is the researcher/institution hoping to gain from this action?
- Experiences – How is the current state working? What can we alter/change to meet our aims and values?

Overall, researchers genuinely value the importance in data management, but their experiences so far have been constrained by resources or are met with procedural speed-bumps and roadblocks. The proposed actions should lower a barrier, leading to a shift in culture to a more desired state through impacting a change in Experiences.

The ideal RDM culture state was identified and described through:

- Workshops with RDM support staff at Griffith
- Analysis of current state documentation
- Consultation with other universities

The current culture towards RDM at Griffith was identified and documented through:

- An RDM Survey was sent to all academic staff – 170 respondents (~6% of researchers)
- 1:1 Interviews with nominated and volunteers – 20 participants (~0.6% of researchers)
- A self-evaluation against the Research Infrastructure Self Evaluation (RISE)
- Workshops with RDM support staff at Griffith
- Case studies of existing RDM

Resulting Improvements

The output from this project is an excellent, thorough, systematic investigation on the culture of Research Data Management at Griffith University. The final report will be used as the evidence for future improvement programs in RDM.

Next Steps

The next steps are:

- Review findings from other institutions through outputs of the ARDC Institutional Underpinnings
- Summarise findings into key themes and meta-level issues
- Operational teams to implement minor changes as appropriate
- Formulate a roadmap to review, update and implement proposed actions
- Re-run survey in two years to benchmark changes in current state, allowing us to assess changes in culture after implementing proposed actions.

Project Outputs

Griffith University would like to share learnings about culture and behaviour in our current state, highlighting trends that other universities may investigate in their institutes. These learnings are based on results from a university-wide survey and interviews across all disciplines, with a lens of culture across all topics. The final report is available detailing survey and interview questions as well as summarised results. **Read the final report on the [Culture Element](#).**

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).